

Table 1: Performance metrics for **NovoMolGen** on the random validation set (mean over three random seeds). The baselines for CharRNN, VAE, and JT-VAE are sourced from Polykovskiy et al. [2020], while the results for LIMO, MolGen-7B, and GP-Molformer are taken from Ross et al. [2024]. **Blue** denotes the best performing model, while **Pink** represents the second-best performing model (p value < 0.05). Avg Rank is computed across all seven metrics within the NovoMolGen family only (lower is better).

REPRESENTATION	TOKENIZATION	MODEL SIZE	Valid (↑)	IntDiv (↑)	Novelty (↑)	FCD (↓)	SNN (↑)	Frag (↑)	Scaff (↑)	Avg Rank (↓)
<i>Train</i>	–	–	1.000	1.000	0.0	0.0376	0.4657	0.9999	0.5144	–
CHARRNN [Polykovskiy et al., 2020]	Atomwise	–	0.9748	0.856	–	0.0732	0.6015	0.9998	0.9242	–
VAE [Polykovskiy et al., 2020]	Atomwise	–	0.9767	0.855	–	0.0990	0.6257	0.9994	0.9386	–
JT-VAE [Jin et al., 2018]	Atomwise	–	1.000	0.855	–	0.3954	0.5477	0.9965	0.8964	–
LIMO [Eckmann et al., 2022]	Atomwise	–	1.000	0.854	–	26.78	0.2464	0.6989	0.0079	–
MOLGEN-7B [Fang et al., 2023]	Atomwise	7B	1.000	0.855	–	0.0435	0.5138	0.9999	0.6538	–
GP-MOLFORMER [Ross et al., 2024]	Atomwise	46.8M	1.000	0.865	0.390	0.0591	0.5045	0.9998	0.7383	–
NovoMOLGEN-SMILES	Atomwise	32M	0.999	0.851	0.983	0.0394	0.4657	0.9999	0.5309	4.50
		157M	0.999	0.851	0.981	0.0426	0.4656	0.9999	0.5200	6.36
		300M	0.999	0.851	0.981	0.0419	0.4657	0.9999	0.5219	5.64
	BPE	32M	0.999	0.851	0.982	0.0384	0.4654	0.9999	0.5182	5.86
		157M	0.999	0.852	0.980	0.0384	0.4655	0.9999	0.5193	5.43
		300M	0.999	0.851	0.979	0.0380	0.4657	0.9999	0.5173	5.86
NovoMOLGEN-SELFIES	Atomwise	32M	1.000	0.852	0.982	0.0799	0.4651	0.9996	0.4765	6.93
	BPE	32M	1.000	0.851	0.984	0.0386	0.4649	0.9999	0.5105	5.71
NovoMOLGEN-DEEPSMILES	Atomwise	32M	0.999	0.851	0.981	0.0400	0.4661	0.9999	0.5218	5.46
	BPE	32M	0.997	0.851	0.982	0.0380	0.4655	0.9999	0.5165	6.29
NovoMOLGEN-SAFE	Atomwise	32M	0.957	0.853	0.953	0.9475	0.4562	0.9955	0.4521	10.43
	BPE	32M	0.997	0.852	0.976	0.3283	0.4599	0.9972	0.4913	9.64

References

- Peter Eckmann, Kunyang Sun, Bo Zhao, Mudong Feng, Michael Gilson, and Rose Yu. LIMO: Latent Inceptionism for Targeted Molecule Generation. In *Proceedings of the 39th International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 5777–5792. PMLR, June 2022. URL <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v162/eckmann22a.html>. ISSN: 2640-3498.
- Yin Fang, Ningyu Zhang, Zhuo Chen, Lingbing Guo, Xiaohui Fan, and Huajun Chen. Domain-Agnostic Molecular Generation with Chemical Feedback. October 2023. URL <https://openreview.net/forum?id=9rPyHyjfwP>.
- Wengong Jin, Regina Barzilay, and Tommi Jaakkola. Junction Tree Variational Autoencoder for Molecular Graph Generation. In *Proceedings of the 35th International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 2323–2332. PMLR, July 2018. URL <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v80/jin18a.html>. ISSN: 2640-3498.
- Daniil Polykovskiy, Alexander Zhebrak, Benjamin Sanchez-Lengeling, Sergey Golovanov, Oktai Tatanov, Stanislav Belyaev, Rauf Kurbanov, Aleksey Artamonov, Vladimir Aladinskiy, Mark Veselov, Artur Kadurin, Simon Johansson, Hongming Chen, Sergey Nikolenko, Alán Aspuru-Guzik, and Alex Zhavoronkov. Molecular Sets (MOSES): A Benchmarking Platform for Molecular Generation Models. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11, December 2020. ISSN 1663-9812. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2020.565644. URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/pharmacology/articles/10.3389/fphar.2020.565644/full>. Publisher: Frontiers.
- Jerret Ross, Brian Belgodere, Samuel C. Hoffman, Vijil Chenthamarakshan, Youssef Mroueh, and Payel Das. GP-MoLFormer: A Foundation Model For Molecular Generation, April 2024. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2405.04912>. arXiv:2405.04912 [q-bio].